

D5.5 — Report of “Framework for achieving import of non-sensitive reference data and software components obtained from external sources and deployed infrastructure for ELIXIR BioContainers repository in secure compute environments”

An ELIXIR Norway ELIXIR3 deliverable

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Context

This report provides the final update for Deliverable 5.5, “Framework for achieving import of non-sensitive reference data and software components obtained from external sources and deployed infrastructure for ELIXIR BioContainers repository in secure compute environments”.

The deliverable has focused on how externally maintained, non-sensitive resources, such as reference data and BioContainers, can be made available inside secure compute environments. The main technical approach evaluated was the use of CVMFS (CernVM-File System) to provide controlled, read-only access to shared software and reference resources in Trusted Research Environments such as TSD.

This report builds on the previous D5.5 report from 2024¹, and adds the final practical outcome: a successful proof-of-concept in which Galaxy CVMFS BioContainers were accessed and executed inside TSD/Colossus.

Background

Secure compute environments restrict direct internet access and uncontrolled software installation to protect sensitive research data. This creates challenges for bioinformatics workflows, which often depend on many software packages, reference genomes, indexes, annotations, and container images.

CVMFS provides a suitable model for distributing such non-sensitive resources. It allows centrally maintained, read-only repositories to be mounted inside compute environments. The Galaxy CVMFS repositories are particularly relevant because they already provide large collections of bioinformatics reference data and BioContainers.

The D5.5 work therefore explored whether this model could support secure analysis environments by making standardized non-sensitive software components available without importing them manually into each project.

Current challenges

Trusted Research Environments impose strict controls on data movement, network access, software installation, and user permissions. These controls are necessary, but they create practical barriers for workflow reproducibility and software maintenance.

Key challenges include:

- lack of direct internet access inside secure environments;
- difficulty installing complex bioinformatics software stacks on demand;
- need for versioned and auditable software and reference resources;
- differences between container runtimes such as Singularity and Apptainer;
- need to align with HPC scheduling and module systems;
- differences between secure compute environments such as TSD, HUNT Cloud, and SAFE.

The practical question for D5.5 was whether CVMFS-hosted resources could be made available in a secure environment in a way that is useful for real workflow execution.

Delivery

The work under D5.5 delivered the following:

Evaluation of TRE requirements

¹ [10.5281/zenodo.10697470](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10697470)

The project evaluated requirements for using externally maintained non-sensitive resources inside Trusted Research Environments, with particular attention to TSD. This included security, network, storage, and compute considerations.

Assessment of CVMFS as a delivery mechanism

CVMFS was assessed as a mechanism for distributing non-sensitive reference data and software components into secure environments. The Galaxy CVMFS² repositories were of particular interest because they provide bioinformatics resources, including reference data and containerized tools.

Dialogue with secure compute providers

Discussions were carried out with secure compute environments, including TSD and related platforms, to clarify how CVMFS-based access to non-sensitive software and reference resources could be provided in practice.

Practical testing in TSD/Colossus

A practical proof-of-concept was carried out in the TSD project [p3066](#), using the Colossus submit host [p3066-hpc-01](#).

The Galaxy CVMFS BioContainers repository was visible inside the environment at:

```
/cvmfs/singularity.galaxyproject.org/all
```

Several BioContainers required by an existing ATAC-seq Snakemake workflow³ were confirmed to be available, including:

```
fastqc:0.11.9--hdfd78af_1
multiqc:1.10.1--py_0
trimmomatic:0.39--1
bowtie2:2.4.5--py39hd2f7db1_2
samtools:1.6--hb116620_7
deeptools:3.5.0--py_0
picard:2.23.3--0
macs2:2.2.7.1--py39hbf8eff0_5
bedtools:2.30.0--hc088bd4_0
ucsc-bedgraphtobigwig:377--h446ed27_1
```

A direct manual test of a Galaxy CVMFS BioContainer was successful:

```
apptainer exec /cvmfs/singularity.galaxyproject.org/all/fastqc:0.11.9--hdfd78af_1 fastqc
--version
```

² <https://galaxyproject.org/admin/reference-data-repo>

³ <https://gitlab.com/epigen/atacseqfastqtoreadcounts>

This returned:

FastQC v0.11.9

This confirmed that the BioContainers repository was not only visible, but that container images could be executed inside the secure compute environment through Apptainer.

Link to workflow execution

The D5.5 framework was further tested by a workflow proof-of-concept in which an existing ATAC-seq Snakemake workflow was imported into TSD and configured to use Galaxy CVMFS BioContainers. The workflow successfully executed initial setup and raw-data quality-control steps, including FastQC and MultiQC, from CVMFS-hosted containers.

Outcomes

The D5.5 work produced the following outcomes:

1. Confirmation that CVMFS-based BioContainer access is feasible in TSD/Colossus

Testing confirmed that the Galaxy CVMFS BioContainers repository can be accessed from within the TSD/Colossus environment used for the proof-of-concept. Container images could be resolved from the CVMFS mount and executed through Apptainer.

2. Demonstration of framework usefulness for real workflows

The framework was validated through an existing Snakemake workflow. This is important because the value of CVMFS in secure compute environments depends on whether it can support real researcher workflows, not only whether resources can be mounted.

3. Reduced need for ad-hoc software import

By using centrally maintained BioContainers from CVMFS, the workflow avoided manually importing and maintaining individual container files inside the secure environment. This supports a more sustainable and reproducible model for software provisioning.

4. Basis for workflow implementation in sensitive computing

The D5.5 framework directly enabled later workflow testing. The proof-of-concept established a practical execution pattern:

1. import workflow source code into TSD through approved mechanisms;
2. use the secure HPC submit host for execution;
3. use Snakemake for workflow orchestration;

4. resolve container images from Galaxy CVMFS;
5. execute containers through Apptainer;
6. keep sensitive data inside the secure project area.

Conclusion

D5.5 has established and tested a framework for making non-sensitive software components, including ELIXIR/Galaxy BioContainers, available inside secure compute environments.

The final proof-of-concept confirms that Galaxy CVMFS BioContainers can be accessed and executed inside TSD/Colossus through Apptainer. This demonstrates that the framework is practically usable for workflow execution and provides a foundation for implementing existing workflows and toolkits for sensitive computing.

The work supports a reproducible and secure model in which sensitive data remain inside the Trusted Research Environment, while standardized non-sensitive software components are provided through controlled, read-only infrastructure.